

Using the Coupling Constant Equation and 8-Theory to Predict the Exact Mass of the Graviton

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Abstract:

By analyzing the coupling constant equation in its first and second representation, i.e. net variations and spin, it becomes evident that an equivalence relation between gravitons and gluons arise. That equivalence is in the amount of terms appearing in the overall form of the coupling magnitude. Thus an additional reinforcement to previous result correlation additional term to the Higgs field.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (2)$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ... \quad (3)$$

In the 8-theory framework, even amounts of manifold variations vanish. That feature allowed the following shift:

$$8 + (1) \rightarrow (1) \quad (4)$$

We know that the strong interaction has eight gauge fields mediating it. Those mediating particles do not carry mass. We also know that gravity has spin two. By switching to the second representation of the equation, we can represent gravity as the following:

$$[(2N(\text{gravity})) + (3)] + N(V) + N(V') + N(V'') = \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \quad (5)$$

$$[2N(\text{gravity}) + 2] \rightarrow [2N(\text{gravity})] \quad (6)$$

Since even amount of variations vanish we will be left with one term in the final form of the term. That is similar to the strong interactions but immensely weaker. Since the bosons mediating the strong interaction are massless, and we can represent it in one term given the coupling constant equation, and by the analysis gravitation has only one term as well, we can reach a mathematical prediction, which will state, that gravitons has no mass. In agreement with reality and agreement with quantum field theory. The only thing taken from what was known before was the fact that the bosons mediating the strong interaction are massless.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Grand Theory of Everything" In: (2021)